

MarketPlace- a Digital Materials Modelling Marketplace

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1. Origin

MarketPlace¹ is an online digital platform connecting providers and consumers of materials modelling tools, services, and related data. Digital marketplaces in general are online platforms that support and streamline transactions between sellers and buyers of products and services. (Shah, 2021). The aim of the Materials Modelling Marketplace is to orchestrate the exchange of tangible and intangible assets to accelerate innovation based on materials modelling.

MarketPlace emanates from an EU Horizon 2020 NMBP Work Programme call, H2020 NMBP-25-2017² - *Next generation system integrating tangible and intangible materials model components to support innovation in industry*. This call specifically asked for the establishment of a “web-based marketplace linking various activities and databases on models, information on simulation tools, communities, expertise, course materials, lectures, seminars and tutorials for at least two manufacturing sectors of the European industry.” The European Materials Modelling Council, EMMC,³ with its consultation activities, was significantly involved in the marketplace idea, which was expressed in its roadmaps⁴, and welcomed by the wider stakeholder community (Figure 1). Besides MarketPlace, VIMMP⁵ was also awarded funding and at the beginning of 2018, both projects embarked on the development of digital marketplaces for the field of materials modelling.

Figure 1. MarketPlace and VIMMP under the umbrella of the EMMC.

¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/760173>, <https://www.the-marketplace-project.eu/>

² https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_NMBP-25-2017

³ European Materials Modelling Council, www.emmc.eu

⁴ <https://emmc.eu/emmc-roadmaps/>

⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/760907>, <https://www.vimmp.eu/>

2. Drivers and benefits of a materials modelling marketplace

The main driver for a marketplace covering the field of materials modelling is the trend towards data and model-based design and development. Industry is seeking a more digital, model-driven approach in order to accelerate innovation and satisfy ever more complex sets of requirements for materials, processes, and products. This can mean substitution of critical elements (rare in abundance or due to geopolitical issues) with more abundant and widely accessible ones, faster and eco-friendly processes, and holistic approaches to capture the whole lifetime of a material, ideally from cradle-to-cradle.

However, the challenges faced by industry are (a) the need for specific expertise and (b) a very heterogeneous, fragmented market of providers of data and models. Materials modelling is characterised by the need for expert/niche knowledge. In order to connect this expertise to business problems, an intermediary step defining the scope and detail of the modelling by introducing so-called translators (Klein, et al., 2021) might also be required. Digital platforms can help industry locate and connect with such expertise in an efficient manner, be it in translation of innovation challenges to materials modelling solutions or with niche knowledge in specific modelling applications.

Furthermore, MarketPlace offers a substantial value to both providers and consumers by reducing barriers and overheads in a fragmented market. Indeed, the materials modelling market (Goldbeck & Simperler, 2020) is dominated by many small enterprises (up to 50 employees) making up about 76 % of the players, who could profit from offering their software tools and services on MarketPlace. There are also providers of free and open-source software (FOSS) which is often limited to highly skilled consumers, as it is often provided without user support. Novice consumers may require more expertise, training or bespoke solutions making modelling available to the non-expert. Such solutions and support will be provided on MarketPlace.

3. Operational Concept

MarketPlace brings together providers (sellers) and consumers (buyers) on an online digital platform (Figure 2). The platform will be operated by a not-for-profit association (see Section 8), which will also oversee its continuous development. The association will be funded mainly by membership payments and participation in government funded projects. It may in future own a subsidiary able to carry out commercial transactions (e.g., based on commissions), with any profits flowing back to support the association.

Figure 2. Generic Scheme of the MarketPlace Actors

MarketPlace links to various materials modelling activities and protagonists, including experts, training, translators, simulation tools, and modelling workflows. At a later stage, a widening to data repositories and other offerings deemed essential for materials modelling is planned.

MarketPlace has developed an online digital platform that can incorporate the entire materials modelling community and its wide range of models, software, and expertise. In particular, translation activities (Hristova-Bogaerds, et al., 2019) (Klein, et al., 2021) play a key role, as well as improving access to all aspects regarding models, i.e., software, expertise, and supporting complex simulation workflows utilising open simulation platforms. Hence, it aims to transform a currently highly fragmented landscape of software, data, and knowledge from a wide range of providers into a coherent system.

Integration is achieved by building on the foundations of terminology, classification and metadata established by the Review of Materials Modelling (de Baas, A., 2017) and the related CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA 17284, 2018). Further formalisation of the semantics has led to sets of ontologies⁶ supporting key functions of MarketPlace. Advanced semantic knowledge services are utilised to provide connections between marketplace clients looking for software, data, translators and experts, (Del Nostro, Goldbeck, Pozzi, & Toti, 2023) and relevant providers much more efficiently and effectively.

⁶ <https://github.com/emmo-repo/OIE-Ontologies>, <https://zenodo.org/record/4411422>

4. MarketPlace Stakeholders, Providers and Consumers

The range of stakeholders seeking these services is quite broad, including

- Experimental Materials Scientists
- R&D Managers
- Formulators/Technicians
- Modellers Translators

While most of these roles can be found in academia and industry, the key 'consumers' that MarketPlace wants to reach are industrial researchers and R&D managers in companies with high R&D intensity and/or large R&D budgets.

All these potential consumers may want to type free text, e.g., "*amorphous materials*", and expect that MarketPlace provides a software solution, potential service provider (training and support), and some papers or tutorials for self-training. The above listed fictitious consumers might be satisfied with a database about materials properties of these amorphous organic materials, or they might want to know how to produce them cheaper, or how to model them using some suitable software.

An important stakeholder group using the MarketPlace are Materials Modelling *Translators*. They will be content with the same type of input fields, but also will require different information on return. A typical scenario for a Translator could be: "*My client wants me to model glass transition temperatures of amorphous organic materials. I need info about software that can do this and costs and licensing.*" Thus, the MarketPlace first needs to identify suitable software at all and eventually needs to show the licensing options of each software for the Translator. In a first step, the MarketPlace already can identify software tools being technically suitable. Legal and licensing information as well as business aspects, however, will be part of future extensions.

The MarketPlace should aid Software Owners (SWOs) willing to offer their services. Many SWOs have marketing departments and/or business developers. Hence, MarketPlace may not be an obvious choice for them. However, there are entrepreneurs/SWOs who are single-person companies or SMEs, and for them MarketPlace could be the right place to start and/or to promote their business. However, there are opportunities for SWOs who are well established. They may want to consider offering multiscale/multistep workflows they developed during (EU) projects comprising several licenses, companies involved, multiple ownership, or some legacy software people do not stop using, or simply a product which is more experimental, out of the box, and does not fit with their usual clients. MarketPlace as an Open Innovation Environment (Goldbeck G. , Simperler, Boskovic, & Aleksic, 2022) and an entrance gate to the global world of the materials modelling market wants them to synergise with their competitors and jointly create novel solutions, as symbolically depicted in Figure 3.

Contributions from individual SWOs ...

... and create a novel solution.

Figure 3. Contributions from several competing SWOs can be synergised on MarketPlace to a novel solution.

The MarketPlace offers a simple registration for any SWO or Expert as outlined below. Structured information is requested at time of registration to support matching a problem owner with a particular SWO or combination of SWOs.

5. MarketPlace features

MarketPlace enables providers to supply and consumers to **explore** tools and experts and knowledge. It supports matching consumers with suitable providers and vice versa. It permits **interaction** between two or more parties, orchestrate an overarching business environment to harmonise business models of different providers, and permit creation of new products and services. Consumers can **create** Apps and/or **execute** them to **improve materials, processes, and products** in Europe and beyond. (Figure 4)

Figure 4. The four pillars of MarketPlace: Explore - Create and Execute - Interact - Improve

The landing page to MarketPlace is depicted in Figure 5 and shows on the top several tiles (hyperlinks) leading to functionalities described in the sections below.

Figure 5. The Landing Page of MarketPlace

5.1. Create

“Create” (Figure 6) leads the consumer to a menu for entity registration. Such items represent real-world entities such as organizations and experts and are referred to as *Knowledge Items*. Once registered, Knowledge Items become visible to other MarketPlace consumers. In the Create page, the consumer can select a type of a Knowledge Item, for which a new entity could be registered. The currently supported types are described as follows:

- Organisation – e.g., labs, companies.
- Expert – e.g., modellers, translators.
- App – offers interactivity to users, e.g., simulation engines, databases, or nested apps

Figure 6. The Create Page

5.2. Knowledge Services - A dictionary of tools, experts, and expertise

Knowledge Services on MarketPlace include information on software tools, models, experts and expertise, communities, educational materials (including webinars), lectures and tutorials. “Via the “Explore” feature depicted in Figure 7, consumers can search for terms and use filters regarding the source that holds the information and if they wish to find experts, organisations, apps, or workflows.

Figure 7. The Explore page of the MarketPlace

The MarketPlace includes information and options to query and to combine queries on:

- software solutions
- repositories and data services
- expertise
- experts
- training materials
- organisations, laboratories, and HPC centres
- models
- materials relations

5.3. Applications and application stores

A range of modelling tools and solutions can be accessed via an application store (Figure 8). Following the unified MarketPlace authorisation procedure, the application store can be reached by clicking on the “Store” tile (Figure 5). Based on the product type, one can view the available list of applications and then access the knowledge item of interest by clicking on the tile “Item page”. Alternatively, a specific application is accessible by utilising the integrated search service of the platform provided that the necessary keywords are entered. A screenshot presented in Figure 8 shows a card deck of available Apps.

Figure 8. The Application Store

Each application comprises an informative element so that a consumer is offered the opportunity to be introduced to its scientific background, functionality, and infrastructure.

Once a product is selected, the consumer is directed to a page with a detailed description of the item. The interface is designed to include individual sections comprising a description, contact

information of the applications' owner/provider, and a logo to aid with visual identification and recognition.

In the case of applications requiring a licence, consumers need to acquire license keys directly from the SWOs/distributors. MarketPlace provides an opportunity for academic SWOs to launch software to a wider audience, which will support the impact and long-term sustainability of academic software developments in materials modelling.

The consumers are provided with information on:

- A "Summary", where the problem description for the corresponding use case is provided.
- A "Domain" of applicability to outline modelling information, such as materials, methods, processes, and utilised software.
- "Connections" to other knowledge items in the platform database, e.g., modelling experts, organizations, applications.

In summary, the services currently provided by MarketPlace include finding Experts and Consultancy Services, Software tools, workflows and models, and Education/Training.

Future developments that are being explored comprise:

- Match making
- Data Services
- Workflow Visualisation
- Conferences and Event Listings
- Rating Functionality

5.4. Beyond the Platform

The bottom of the landing page points towards a GitHub repository⁷ and User docs, respectively. (Figure 9)

Figure 9. Useful links, located at the bottom of the landing page.

⁷ <https://github.com/materials-marketplace/>

Publicly available content on the Materials MarketPlace GitHub includes:

- a Standard API⁸ defined for registered applications, which can be used as basis for the interaction between applications on the Materials MarketPlace platform.
- A Python Software Development Kit (SDK)⁹ to communicate with the Materials MarketPlace platform. It consists of all the available capabilities implemented as python functions. It enables users to create a python instance of a registered application and simply call the supported capabilities associated with it via class methods with appropriate inputs.
- The MarketPlace HPC Gateway application¹⁰, which enables users to interact with High Performance Computers (HPCs) through a MarketPlace proxy using the HPC gateway SDK, as many calculation-intensive modelling workflows require means beyond a standard desktop computer.

The “User docs” link leads to documentation about the MarketPlace platform where one finds all the information regarding its usage. The tiles on the landing page are depicted in Figure 10, and offer an introduction to the platform, a list of capabilities supported by the MarketPlace, advice how one can add an application, and a direct link to support.

Figure 10. Middle section of the "MarketPlace Docs" landing page

⁸ <https://github.com/materials-marketplace/standard-app-api>

⁹ <https://github.com/materials-marketplace/python-sdk>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/materials-marketplace/hpc-gateway-app>

6. Use Cases

MarketPlace project has included six use cases in fields such as additive manufacturing of super-alloys, screen-printing process, nanomaterials for catalyst applications, ceramic injection moulding for medical applications, printing of photovoltaic thin-film, and 3D printing of metals and alloys for powder metallurgy. The outcome of some of these use cases may be found as applications on the MarketPlace and these apps can serve as templates to develop similar types of apps and use cases by future users of the MarketPlace.

The participating partners and their shorthand are listed below:

Fraunhofer Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung e.V. (**FRAUNHOFER**)

ACCESS e.V. (**ACCESS**)

Robert Bosch GmbH (**BOSCH**)

CRYSTALSOL OU (**CRYSTALSOL**)

DCS Computing GmbH (**DCS**)

Ecole Polytechnique Federale de Lausanne (**EPFL**)

GRANTA DESIGN Ltd - now ANSYS (**GRANTA**)

Haute Ecole Specialisee de Suisse Occidentale (**HES**)

Johnson Matthey PLC (**JM**)

L'Urederra Fundacion para el Desarrollo Tecnologico y Social (**LUREDERRA**)

MBN NANOMATERIALIA SPA (**MBN**)

MTU AERO ENGINES AG (**MTU**)

Norges Teknisk-Naturvitenskapelige Universitet (**NTNU**)

Stiftelsen SINTEF (**SINTEF**)

University College London (**UCL**)

6.1. Use case 1 – Additive Manufacturing of Super-Alloys (MTU with teams from FRAUNHOFER, ACCESS, Ansys-GRANTA, and EPFL)

An additive manufacturing technique that is steadily gaining importance is so-called laser powder bed fusion (L-PBF). In this process, one or more laser beams are used to create the three-dimensional structure to be built up in a powder bed by melting the powder particles. (Figure 11)

Figure 11. Schematic of relevant phenomena in the L-PBF additive manufacturing process (©C. Bierwisch, Fraunhofer IWM)

The simulation of the L-PBF process is complex due to the occurrence of many interacting physical phenomena. During the L-PBF process, a laser beam source locally melts the powder particles, and a melt pool is formed. As the heat source progresses away from the newly formed melt pool the temperature starts decreasing, and the melt pool solidifies again and forms the final part. The melt pool dynamics depend on various, often temperature dependent, physical properties, such as laser uniformity (temporal and spatial), strength, speed, absorption and reflection, surface tension, viscosity, heat capacity, thermal conductivity, and gas phase recoil pressure. A suitable method to comprehensively model the physics in melt pools is the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) method. The temperature history of the L-PBF process leads to complex microstructure formation. Microstructure refers here to the size, shape and orientation of dendritic grains that have formed once the material in the melt pool has re-solidified. The solidification process is governed by a competition between grain nucleation and grain growth. One method to predict microstructure formation is the Phase Field (PF) method which considers local melt pool information, such as state of matter and temperature, to predict grain growth. The Use-case 1 (UC1) application is designed to deliver a simplified and easily accessible tool for studying the influence of laser process parameters on the resulting microstructure for the Nickel-based superalloy Inconel 718. To fulfil this purpose, first an SPH simulation using the software SimPARTIX¹¹ is carried out which yields the spatially and temporally resolved temperature field of the melting and re-solidifying alloy material. Furthermore, the current phase of matter is being tracked. These data are then transferred to a PF simulation using the software MICRESS¹² which calculates microstructure properties of the solidifying alloy by taking thermodynamical material properties into account.

On the current MarketPlace, the UC1 application encompasses three main components, namely Jupyter Notebook¹³ utilizing Viola¹⁴ as frontend UI and SimPARTIX and MICRESS as the workflow orchestrator and SimPARTIX and MICRESS as simulation web services. The workflow orchestrator provides a graphical consumer interface guiding the consumer through the simulation process. Both simulation software tools, SimPARTIX and MICRESS, are accessed and controlled using a respective

¹¹ <https://www.simpartix.com/>

¹² <https://micress.rwth-aachen.de/>

¹³ <https://blog.jupyter.org/and-voil%C3%A0-f6a2c08a4a93>

¹⁴ <https://github.com/voila-dashboards/voila>

web service. The service is realized using the Flask Python library. It implements the MarketPlace REST API (Gillis, 2020) for initializing, running, querying, and stopping melt pool simulations as well as retrieving simulated datasets. Complementary, the MICRESS web service provides the same set of functionalities for the solidification simulations. The interface is declared by Python scripts and Jupyter Notebook¹⁵ files. A schematic workflow of the UC1 application is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12. A schematic workflow using voila leading to the SimPARTIX and MICRESS web service.

In order to transfer data between SimPARTIX and MICRESS, a mapping is used to transfer the particle-based melt pool data of a certain time frame onto a Cartesian grid. Unique relations between the transferred data within the application on one side and entities from the Elementary Multiperspective Material Ontology (EMMO)¹⁶ on the other side have been identified. Table 1 summarises these relations including the respective Internationalized Resource Identifiers (IRI). (Dürst & Suignard, 2005)

¹⁵ <https://jupyter.org/>

¹⁶ formerly European Materials & Modelling Ontology, <https://github.com/emmo-repo/EMMO>

Use Case 1 data quantity	EMMO 1.0.0-beta entity	EMMO 1.0.0-beta IRI
Group (powder particle)	Index	http://emmo.info/emmo#EMMO_0cd58641_824c_4851_907f_f4c3be76630c
StateOfMatter	StateOfMatter	http://emmo.info/emmo#EMMO_b9695e87_8261_412e_83cd_a86459426a28
Temperature	ThermodynamicTemperature	http://emmo.info/emmo#EMMO_affe07e4_e9bc_4852_86c6_69e26182a17f

Table 1. Relations between UC1 application data and EMMO identifiers.

The DLite¹⁷ container format has been identified as suitable to store and send the semantically annotated data within the Use Case 1 workflow. A so-called DLite schema in JSON format needs to be declared in order to define the layout of the data being transferred. The DLite Python library is then used in the application workflow to save or import the actual simulation data, which is again realized by means of JSON¹⁸ files. By providing semantic mappings via an agreed-upon standard (such as EMMO), a higher level of interoperability is achieved in that it liberates the application developers of UC1 from the need to coordinate with each other. Instead, they independently annotate their data using the common language provided by the ontology. As an illustration, in UC1 the temperature gradient is needed for the MICRESS application but not provided explicitly in the output of SimPARTIX. A transformation function in the AiiDALab application has been designed to process the temperature information coming from SimPARTIX and to produce the gradient which will be sent to MICRESS. The semantic mappings are useful for understanding the data schemas by humans as well as enabling semantic transformations by machines.

A full documentation of the implementation can be found on github.¹⁹

¹⁷ <https://github.com/SINTEF/dlite/pkgs/container/dlite%2Fdlite-stages>

¹⁸ <https://www.json.org/json-en.html>

¹⁹ <https://github.com/materials-marketplace/user-docs/blob/42-add-uc-documentation/docs/source/ucs/uc1.md>

6.2. Use case 2 – Simulation of screen-printing process for solid oxide fuel cells (BOSCH with teams from DCS, FRAUNHOFER, EPFL, ACCESS, GRANTA, HES, and SINTEF)

Use-case 2 (UC2) consists of the simulation of viscoelastic pastes used in screen printing for solid oxide fuel cells. (Figure 13)

Figure 13. Illustration of the screen-printing process.

Due to the complexity of the viscoelastic material, with its highly non-linear behaviour, and the high computational cost required to simulate each individual step in the process, it was decided early on that work in the use case would focus exclusively on the levelling stage of the screen-printing process. The levelling stage determines the final quality of the print as the paste spread is an important parameter. Paste spreading is strongly dependent on paste properties, so a simulation of the levelling process is ideal for testing different pastes and defining admissible ranges for material properties for given a quality requirement with minimal experimentation.

The workflow for this use case consists of three steps. First, experimental rheometer data for a certain paste is taken as input for a parameter optimization script. The Giesekus constitutive model (Giesekus, 1982) is used to determine the materials properties required for the simulation. The second step is a simulation of the rheometer. The constitutive properties from the parameter optimization are used in an OpenFOAM²⁰ simulation with RheoTools²¹, where the rheometer is simulated, and the results are compared with the experimental data for validation of the obtained constitutive properties. In the final third step, the same constitutive properties are used for a full

²⁰ <https://www.openfoam.com/>

²¹ <https://github.com/fppimenta/rheoTool>

multiphase simulation of paste levelling, which is allowed to settle under gravity for the in-silico measurement of its spread.

The workflow allows a consumer, given a set of experimental rheometer data for a certain viscoelastic paste, to automatically calculate its constitutive properties and use them to simulate the levelling process, given output on how much levelling has been achieved.

The Paste Levelling application is built on top of this workflow, automating the three steps into a seamless sequence, with no consumer input in-between each of the steps. The application consists internally of a series of Python modules which handle the different steps of the workflow, as illustrated in Figure 14 below.

Figure 14. Schematic of the Paste Levelling App

The first step, the parameter optimization, generates the output with the constitutive properties used in the OpenFOAM simulations of both the rheometer and levelling steps. The rheometer is another Python script which handles the multiple simulations required to go over the range of frequencies and amplitudes required to reproduce the experimental rheometer data. Finally, the levelling simulation is a prepared OpenFOAM case setup that only takes the different constitutive properties as required input to run the case. This step uses a REST API to communicate with the MarketPlace platform and the HPC App, which handles the remote execution of the parallel job.

Figure 15 below shows the user input for the application, which just requires a few material properties and uploading of the files with the experimental data from the rheometer. Once that is supplied to the application and the user runs it, it will internally execute the steps outlined in the previous paragraph. The user can also define a few simulation parameters, such as the timestep, final simulation time and how often to output data.

Figure 15. Paste Levelling application screen with consumer inputs to run the simulation.

After running the simulation, the consumer can access the postprocessing of the data, as shown in Figure 16. The upper row of plots shows the rheometer results, comparing the simulated rheometer data with the provided experimental data. The lower row of plots shows the paste levelling results. The normalized broadening of the paste, i.e., its width change divided by the original width (bottom left) as well as a comparison of the paste profile at start and end of the simulation (bottom right) is shown.

Figure 16. Post-processed results of the simulation executed by the Paste Levelling App.

6.3. Use case 3 – *Nanomaterials for catalyst applications* (JM with teams from SINTEF, LUREDERRA, and Ansys-GRANTA)

The intention of the apps developed in Use-case 3 (UC3) is to accelerate the development and testing of catalysts for methane oxidation using catalyst supports produced by Flame Spray Pyrolysis (FSP). (Teoh, Amal, & Mädler, 2010) Four different apps were developed; they can be either used individually or as part of a workflow.

The purpose of the **FSP application** is to allow a FSP operator to assess how changing the many operating parameters of the reactor (e.g., pressure drop, dispersion gas flow rate, precursor composition and flow rate, fan extraction rate, etc.) will affect the primary particle size of the powder that is produced. The particle size is an important quantity to be able to predict since it influences the performance of the nanoparticles when used as a catalyst support. Additionally, the simulation provides qualitative information regarding the flame temperature and velocity, which will help the operator to better understand the physical conditions that influence the reactor performance. For the FSP app, a computational fluid dynamics (CFD) model using ANSYS Fluent²² is employed which tightly-couples a continuum model for the gas flow to a discrete-particle model for the precursor spray. In addition, the continuum model for the gas flow is one-way coupled to another continuum model which solves the evolution of the nanoparticles through nucleation, agglomeration and sintering using a population balance model. Figure 17 shows qualitative simulation results and validation against experimental results for five different production conditions evaluated by Lurederra.

Figure 17. Simulation results obtained by SINTEF for the FSP production of nano-alumina carried out by Lurederra. Top-left: Comparison of primary particle sizes of FSP powders from simulations and experiments. Top-right: Ratio between experimental and simulated particle sizes. Bottom: Contour plots of the temperature for different productions (blue = 300 K, red = 3300 K).

²² <https://www.ansys.com/products/fluids/ansys-fluent>

Many catalyst developers use experimental rigs where a small catalyst sample is placed in a packed bed reactor and tested under different operating conditions. These rigs are good for high throughput screening of different catalysts, but not for extracting detailed kinetic data due to several non-ideal effects. For catalytic methane oxidation, the most important non-ideal effects are (i) the large amount of heat given off due to the highly exothermic reaction, (ii) rapid heat loss from the small reactor and (iii) internal mass transfer limitations due to rapid reaction at higher temperatures. Considering these effects, the extent of which vary greatly between different reactor systems, the purpose of the **Catalyst kinetics calibration application** is to allow the extraction of (as close as possible to) intrinsic kinetics from such reactors. Kinetic parameters determined in this way, wherein the effects of mass and heat transport have been isolated, will be more robust in simulations of reaction conditions and test-equipment that differ from those used to measure the original catalyst performance. To achieve this, the model's kinetic parameters are obtained by calibrating against experimental data directly in a CFD continuum model (using ANSYS Fluent™) which accounts for the above-mentioned non-ideal effects. An example of the fit that can be achieved against experimental results are shown in Figure 18. In the app, the experimental data to calibrate and validate the model output has been curated using ANSYS Granta MI²³ and thence extracted using a Marketplace registered API. Experimental data provided by JM were curated in a well-defined schema, see Figure 18 (left). Data are stored with full traceability including raw material properties, test parameters, reactor equipment specifics and physical characterisation performed on each prepared catalyst sample (Figure 18 (right)).

Figure 18. Schematic representation of the UC3 data schema (left) and example of contained data (right).

The optimization workflow, implemented in ANSYS optiSlang™²⁴ (Figure 19), queries the data curation app registered with the Marketplace to find tests performed with well-defined parameters, for example, light-off cycle number, steam content or mass of catalyst.

²³ <https://www.ansys.com/products/materials/granta-mi>

²⁴ <https://www.ansys.com/products/connect/ansys-optislang>

Figure 19. Calibration workflow implemented in ANSYS optiSLang. From the left, users can setup query parameters, which are used to query the database implemented in the Data Curation app to prepare the workflow input for the optimization block of the workflow.

The purpose of the **Catalyst test reactor application** is to allow an experimentalist to assess and understand the detailed physical behaviour of their tests, having obtained the reaction kinetic parameters for their specific catalyst from the Catalyst kinetics calibration application. For example, the experimentalist can assess whether significant internal mass transfer limitations are present for the size of the catalyst pellets used or if high temperatures, that may lead to sintering, are found locally. For this purpose, the same continuum model of the catalyst test reactor is used as in the Catalyst kinetics calibration application, only now using known reaction kinetic parameters as input.

Finally, the **Monolith channel application** is intended to allow a catalyst developer to assess, from simulations, the performance of their original powder catalyst in the intended final application in a washcoated (McMahon, 2022) monolith. (Avila, Montes, & Miró, 2005) The only required input is experimental data regarding the catalyst performance in the packed bed reactor. This is beneficial, since the tests performed in the simple packed bed reactor are much faster and less expensive than performing experiments using a highly-engineered reactor suitable for washcoated monoliths. A continuum CFD model was developed in ANSYS Fluent™ for a washcoated monolith channel using the kinetic parameters obtained in the Catalyst kinetics calibration application as input. The model accounts for the heat generated by the exothermic methane oxidation reaction and internal mass transfer limitations by calculating the total effective diffusivity (thermal and material) in the washcoat.

Due to restrictions on the use of proprietary software, the Catalyst kinetics calibration application was not integrated onto the MarketPlace platform. The remaining three apps in UC3 were developed on the MarketPlace platform using AiiDALab as the front-end, with the intention of being run on the HPC infrastructure of the model developer using their software licenses. However, all three apps use the commercial CFD software, ANSYS Fluent™, for which the license agreement does not allow an external party to launch the simulations. Consequently, the app workflow is set up such that, after specifying the app input parameters, the user is given a simulation ID that should be sent to the modeller. The modeller can then launch the app workflow on their HPC cluster using a single command line. The

workflow run by the modeller retrieves the user inputs from an online server, launches the simulation on the HPC cluster with the correct settings and sends the results back to the server. In the meanwhile, the app monitors the server for the simulation results which are displayed to the user upon completion. Documentation of the app implementations²⁵, as well as code²⁶, are available online. Figure 20 shows screenshots from the Catalyst test reactor GUI.

Figure 20. GUI of the Catalyst test reactor app showing (left) specification of the user input and (right) simulation results. The simulation results show significant mass and heat transport limitations at higher conversions of methane.

6.4. Use case 4 – Ceramic Injection Moulding for medical Applications (HES with teams from FRAUNHOFER, DCS, ACCESS, GRANTA, EPFL, and NTNU)

The workflow of this use case comprises three primary subprocesses of Ceramic Injection Moulding (CIM) being simulated: i) the mixing and granulation of the ceramic powder with the polymer binder, ii) the characterization of the feedstock composite, and iii) the injection of the feedstock into the mould. (Figure 21)

²⁵ <https://materials-marketplace.readthedocs.io/en/latest/ucs/uc3.html>

²⁶ <https://github.com/materials-marketplace>

Figure 21. Schematic representation of the CIM process comprising four sub-processes identified as 1) mixing & granulation, 2) injection molding, 3) thermal debinding and 4) sintering. UC4 simulates the first two sub-processes.

The software used to simulate these are Aspherix²⁷, LAMMPS²⁸, and Moldflow²⁹, respectively.

The first application that has been developed is **SimAspherix-App**. Using the Aspherix software as its underlying calculation tool, this application takes as input the material properties for polymer and ceramic materials, particle sizes, and operating conditions of the mixer and conveyor. Employing the discrete element method, it simulates the mixing and granulation process for the determination of the mixing efficiency and the volume fraction of the two components of the feedstock, providing these parameters as output.

The second App, called **SimLAMMPS-App**, utilizes LAMMPS to perform atomistic simulations for the characterization of the feedstock composite. Specifically, the application takes as input the molecular configuration which includes the ceramic particles and the polymer binder based on the

²⁷ <https://www.aspherix-dem.com/software/aspherix/>

²⁸ <https://www.lammps.org/>

²⁹ <https://www.autodesk.com/products/moldflow/overview>

volume fraction provided by the previous App. Through a series of simulations at varying conditions (parametric analysis), SimLAMMPS-App predicts the specific volume of the composite system as a function of temperature and pressure, namely the PVT behaviour.

SimAspherix-App implements the Marketplace API and an additional frontend based on Flask, a Python-based web Application framework. The loading screen of the application is shown in Figure 22 below, which shows the setup for the mixing simulation performed with Aspherix®.

Figure 22. The loading page of the SimAspherix-App, with an image of the mixing step of the workflow.

Currently the API allows modifications to the parameters in the case setup, allowing the consumer to run variations in material properties and operating conditions. This results in a complete definition of the simulation set-up for the use case. This set-up is then passed via a REST API to the HPC app which allows the application to be executed in parallel on a remote HPC resource. The application communicates with the Marketplace platform using the REST API for authentication and job management. This is illustrated in Figure 23.

Figure 23. The consumer input screen in the SimAspherix-App.

Currently the API allows modifications to the parameters in the case setup, allowing the consumer to run variations in material properties and operating conditions. This results in a complete simulation set-up of the use case that is communicated via the REST API of the integrated HPC application to external HPC resources, which allows the submission of parallel jobs. The application communicates with the MarketPlace platform using the REST API for authentication and job management. This is illustrated in Figure 24.

Figure 24. Schematic of the Aspherix and LAMMPS Applications and how they communicate with the MarketPlace platform via the HPC App.

The simulation results can be downloaded after the simulation is complete. This includes the full Discrete Element Method (DEM) simulation, which can be postprocessed in an external software such as ParaView, along with the particle volume fraction results, which are required by the SimLAMMPS-App to perform the next step in the simulation workflow. The SimLAMMPS-App is set up in the same way as the SimAspherix-App, with the exception that Aspherix is replaced by LAMMPS as the solver engine, and the LAMMPS simulation is set-up using a template. The remaining connections with MarketPlace and the HPC application remain the same through the REST API, as shown in Figure 24. Figure 25 below shows the input screen of the LAMMPS App, which allows the consumers to change a few simulation parameters, and upload the required results from the previous step in the workflow.

configuration 1

Here you can input the necessary inputs that will be used for the configuration

The setup will perform several simulation with varying temperatures:

Start temperature (kelvin) End temperature (kelvin)

Number of steps for temperature sweep

Further three different pressure levels are simulated:

First pressure level (pascal)

Second pressure level (pascal)

Third pressure level (pascal)

Please provide a LAMMPS data file generated by the VTK workflow:

LAMMPS data file

During development we allow to modify the number of timesteps for quicker testing

Number of timesteps

Configuration:

- * set input parameters for different operation points of the simulation
- * upload data file generated by VMD approach
- * reduce simulation time for demonstration or testing

Figure 25. The consumer input screen in the SimLAMMPS-App.

Moldflow is a proprietary software not developed by any of the partners involved in MarketPlace, which prevents any modifications or customisation on our end, and makes developing a proper wrapper difficult. It does have an API, but it is geared towards modifying and complementing runs with external calculations, rather than connecting to the solver itself for standard cases.

Besides, Moldflow is essentially a GUI-based software, and though it offers command-line execution capabilities for running in Linux clusters, the documentation itself recommends setting up cases using the GUI and then using the resulting case file as input for a remote run. While not a complete roadblock, this is certainly a hindrance to setting up a fully automated use case which includes Moldflow. In any case, a Moldflow application would be nothing more than taking a previously setup GUI case and running it remotely.

Due to the above reasons, and because it is valuable to demonstrate workflows in which consumer input is required at intermediate steps, an application for Moldflow has not been developed and this remains a manual process in the workflow.

Currently, human intervention is required for the transition between the SimAspherix application and SimLAMMPS-App, and the post processing of the results of SimLAMMPS-App to acquire the final parameters for the PVT constitutive model (Two-Domain Tait) (Autodesk Help, 2017). However, in-house codes written in Tcl³⁰ and Python have already been developed to reduce the complexity of these steps to a minimum level.

³⁰ <https://www.tcl.tk/>

6.5. Use case 5 – *Printing of Photovoltaic (PV) Thin Film (CRYSTALSOL with a team from UCL)*

The purpose of the application and the associated software is to facilitate the understanding of the relationship between the physical properties of Ag nanowires, i.e., electrical conductivity and optical transparency, and experimental parameters such as aspect ratio and densities. The model developed is quite general, not only covering the Ag random nanowire networks, but also nanowires based on other materials, such as carbon nanotubes. The first set of computer codes were developed based on Matlab³¹ (commercial) and Circuitscape³². Initially Matlab was used to produce random nanowires and compute the optical transparency, and Circuitscape was employed to compute the electrical conductivity. In an updated version, the Matlab code was replaced by a non-commercial code based on the Python package Shapely³³, interfacing with the Julia-based³⁴ software Circuitscape. The computed electrical conductivity or sheet resistance and optical transparency can be compared with the experimental results. In addition, the simulations can provide some guidance on how much coating should be applied to the Ag nanowires in the fabrication process. (Meissner, et al., 2023)

To implement the application, we have integrated two types of languages – Julia and Python as a stand-alone software. In the background, we have used the Julia code to implement the production of the random networks, interfacing with the Python Shapely package via PyCall.³⁵ In the frontend (the web application development) we can call the Circuitscape software within Python. Certainly, there are many areas in which we can further improve the App. However, all in all, we have implemented the application but currently not used the MarketPlace API.

6.6. Use case 6 – *3D printing of Metals (MBN with teams from GRANTA and FRAUNHOFER)*

Use-case 6 (UC6) deals with the development of customized steel powder for laser cladding and laser metal deposition techniques, requiring a balanced trade-off between hardness and strength for the produced part. Figure 26 illustrates some of these deposition techniques.

³¹ <https://www.mathworks.com/products/matlab.html>

³² <https://circuitscape.org/>

³³ <https://shapely.readthedocs.io/en/stable/manual.html>

³⁴ <https://julialang.org/>

³⁵ <https://pypi.org/project/pycall/>

(a)

(b)

Figure 26. From left to right: Illustration of μ LMD test at lab scale; set of Laser Cladding trials of high alloyed steel; microstructure image by optical microscopy on AM deposit of modified steel by mechanical alloying (Vilella etching).

Powder feedstock with customised composition is produced by mechanical alloying via High Energy Ball Milling. The feedstock needs to meet certain criteria with regards to morphology and compositional homogeneity to be suitable for AM by powder blown technologies. The materials modelling was expected to provide advantages by narrowing of compositional ranges to test experimentally during the material development phase. This would be achieved through prediction of phase distribution and microstructure by simulation. The overall objective would be to answer customer needs in the automotive sector more efficiently both in time and in expected material performance.

Following the initial translation phase to tackle the use case complexities and select the appropriate modelling approach, an initial scenario was identified, based on thermodynamic considerations of solidification during the additive manufacturing of such steels. Dependent on the alloy composition and cooling rate, the material forms complex microstructures. Usually, there is a high-volume fraction of martensite or bainite due to the high cooling rate, which cannot be predicted by thermodynamic tools not taking kinetics into account. However, retained austenite may be present, too, and the austenite stability windows can be estimated, as well as compositional differences between primary and secondary austenite (“primary”: solidified as austenite, “secondary”: solidified as δ -ferrite and transformed to austenite). Besides, various carbides and intermetallic phases may precipitate. The underlying thermodynamics is evaluated using MatCalc³⁶, and an application for the

³⁶ <https://www.matcalc.at/>

interaction with MatCalc and the post-processing of thermodynamic calculations is being developed and integrated into the MarketPlace platform.

Further modelling blocks including topological distribution of phases and microstructure evolution kinetics during solidification have been identified for a more effective prediction of steel microstructure after additive manufacturing, but they would require additional modelling tools.

The **MatCalc application** allows an easy evaluation of the thermodynamic equilibrium and the thermodynamics during solidification. In order to make the use case accessible to a wide consumer group, the free version of MatCalc is used. Both the software and the required thermodynamic database can be freely used. However, since the free version is limited to three chemical elements, a system consisting of iron, carbon and one additional metal, e.g., chromium, manganese, or nickel, is considered. The application enables the consumer to easily assess the system without any knowledge of thermodynamic calculations and use of MatCalc. The same approach is applicable to the full licence version, enabling a wider range of elements to be included.

As a first step, from the options Cr, Mn, Mo, Ni, and Si, the consumer selects the third element to enter the system. After defining contents of C and the third element (balance is Fe), the application calculates the phase fractions of the stable phases in equilibrium as well as their composition as a function of temperature. Although additive manufacturing is a non-equilibrium process, considering the equilibrium phase diagram provides useful preliminary information. In the example, the C content is varied, which – amongst others – affects the stable phases in the temperature range of solidification. With the lower C content, both δ -ferrite and austenite are stable below the liquidus, whereas with the higher C content, only austenite is stable.

In a next step, the application carries out a Scheil-Gulliver (Chemeurope.com, 2022) calculation to simulate solidification. Starting from the liquid range, the temperature is decreased, and the evolution of the solid phases is calculated until all liquid has solidified. The resulting phase fractions and the composition of the phases after solidification are relevant for the microstructure evolution during further cooling. MatCalc cannot directly predict some key features of microstructure evolution, e.g., the martensitic or bainitic transformation. However, the partition of the elements during solidification affects the transformation kinetics. Therefore, the Scheil-Gulliver calculation provides valuable information about what kind of final microstructures can be expected.

The UC6 application is an AiiDALab based MarketPlace application that connects to a main MatCalc MarketPlace application and it provides a GUI for easier interaction. It allows the consumer to select the third element from a dropdown menu and to enter the weight percentages of C and the third element by means of sliders. The MatCalc application handles the consumer input, creates the input to the MatCalc calculations and writes the result files. The results of the calculations are returned as tabular data in ASCII files, which are displayed in diagrams using matplotlib.pyplot in the AiiDALab App.

The set of experimental data available for UC 6, which have been curated by Ansys-Granta system, includes:

- Chemical composition of the steel alloy, in terms of element content for Fe, C, Cr, Mo, Mn, Ni, Si as main constituting elements;
- Physical properties of powder material, in terms of particle size, morphology and Hall flowability;

- Main process parameters of laser cladding, including laser power, scan speed, pitch, feeding flow;
- Properties from characterizations of the built parts, i.e., size, number of layers, microstructural imaging, spatial distribution of elements by EDX mapping, hardness measurements.

Data curation for use case by Ansys-Granta system allowed to jointly collect and manage data which are usually stored and managed in three separated and independent databases for i) powder material production, ii) additive process and iii) characterisations. The implementation of this increased the efficiency and efficacy of data curation during the development process for a new powder material for laser cladding.

7. MarketPlace Business Model

In the following section we shall discuss how MarketPlace will generate value. Using the findings of (Van Gansen, Valayer, & Allesie, 2018) and using their four platform business model types collaboration, orchestration, creation or matching we can see that MarketPlace will embrace all four of them.

Collaboration: MarketPlace will enable clients to find new partners from different backgrounds, location, ecosystem, knowledge, etc. and explore new ways of working together.

Orchestration: MarketPlace will enable the integration of business processes between clients and providers.

Creation: Providers are invited to create something new on the application store and offer it to clients.

Matching: The MarketPlace will match providers who offer a product/service are matched with consumers who are interested in the offering.

If we apply the findings of (Täuscher, 2016) and their six possible Digital Market Business Models (DMBMs) we can identify five of them to be significant for MarketPlace:

Efficient product transactions: MarketPlace consumers want to find providers offering a product/service of interest and are attracted because our platform simplifies and streamlines a consumer's experience, whether exchanging or networking. Providers, in turn, can access a large consumer base and let the MarketPlace become their channel to market.

Product community: Via the EMMC, we have established a large community around Materials modelling who are knowledgeable. This enables the exchange of information for both provider and consumers: the providers can follow consumer comments and improve their offering and the less knowledgeable consumers can find guidance from expert consumers.

Offline services on-demand: On Market Place it is possible 24/7 to find Service providers, book a service and receive it in person. Some service providers offer **Online services** such as SaaS or Training Events. Also, **Peer-to-peer offline services** will be on offer, as providers are offering consultants, trainers, and translators to customers.

Specifically, MarketPlace aims to become a hub for Collaboration and a curated gateway to the plurality of knowledge and software providers. For materials scientists, MarketPlace provides a one

stop shop for all their modelling needs from software vendors, data repositories and training resources to domain experts and consultants.

The above collaboration and community aspects of MarketPlace are particularly important and are already quite well developed due to the collaborative project and the EMMC community more widely. On the other hand, the aspects of orchestration and efficient product transactions require very high TRL implementation, which goes beyond that achieved at the end of a Horizon 2020 project.

For these and related considerations, MarketPlace intends to sustain its operation and development via an Association (non-profit) legal entity, as described in the following section.

8. MarketPlace Association and its Vision

MarketPlace will launch as an association and its vision (Figure 27) is to leverage software engineering to integrate materials modelling and property/validation databases originating from a specialised and fragmented community into dedicated well integrated workflows that industry and academia can leverage to take on societal challenges now and in the future.

Figure 27. A depiction of MarketPlace's vision

This also provides an opportunity for including a range of digital materials platform technology developments and interests of other related projects into the scope of the association. Of course, specific activities will be decided by the association board once it has been formed.

The following non-profit goals are targeted:

- To improve the interactions between providers and consumers of materials modelling software, services, and expertise.
- To build a community of technology developers, facilitating collaboration on building digital platforms such as digital marketplaces and open innovation environments
- To provide mechanisms for the rapid transfer of materials modelling and academic innovation to end-consumers in industry.

- To facilitate access to the plurality of knowledge and software by any interested beneficiary.
- To collaborate on, support the development of and operated open digital platforms for materials innovation based on data and models.
- To provide knowledge and collaboration services and a gateway to materials databases and modelling activities present and yet to emerge.

The envisaged activities of the association include the following:

- Engage in collaborations to develop, test, and deploy open web-based materials modelling and collaboration platforms.
- Operate a marketplace platform to
 - connect disparate modellers, translators, and manufacturing communities.
 - Provide data and Apps to widen the Application of materials modelling in industry.
 - Provide resources regarding training and translation
- Initiate and coordinate industry-led projects to drive forward materials modelling, including the generation of solution based on modelling workflows to address specific industrial question on a pre-competitive level.

Income to sustain the operation of the MarketPlace association will be generated via **membership** fees as well as via grant funding due to participation in further collaborative projects at national and EU level.

MarketPlace also will offer some of its service for **free** to all, but provides extra, premium features in exchange for a recurring membership fee. The challenge here lies in striking a balance between the services provided free-of-charge and those only accessible via the subscription.

Besides these activities and income sources, the possibilities for listing fees from commercial providers as well as potential for commissions on transactions will be investigated, in as far as these are possible within the remit of an Association.

9. Conclusions and Outlook

The concept, development, and implementation of a digital marketplace for materials modelling in the Horizon 2020 project MarketPlace has been described. The need for and potential impact of such a marketplace is illustrated in six use cases involving complex industrial challenges that can only be addressed by bringing together a range of materials models and related expertise. As studies of the materials modelling market carried out by the project have shown, software and services are provided by a large number of mostly small companies as well as academics. As a result, it is challenging for materials and manufacturing industry (and in particular SMEs) to assemble the necessary tools and knowledge to address advanced materials. Likewise, it is difficult for the small providers to reach their market potential. In response, Materials Marketplace provides value based on the four platform business model types collaboration, orchestration, creation and matching.

The main functions of the current MarketPlace implementation have been presented, in particular its Knowledge Services and Applications, along with an overview of the six use cases. Sustaining and further developing the Materials MarketPlace is envisaged via the foundation of a not-for-profit association. A digital materials marketplace association offers a focal point for collaborations and exchange to serve the growing interest and need of European materials and manufacturing industries to access models and related expertise more easily.

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Acronyms, Abbreviations and Elucidations

API – Application Programming Interface

CEN - European Committee for Standardization (French: Comité Européen de Normalisation), founded 1961.

CFD - Computational Fluid Dynamics

CIM - Ceramic Injection Moulding

CWA - CEN Workshop Agreement

DEM - Discrete Element Method

DLite - is a C implementation of the SINTEF Open Framework and Tools (SOFT), which is a set of concepts and tools for how to efficiently describe and work with scientific data.

DMBM - Digital Market Business Models

EMMC – European Materials Modelling Council

EMMO – Elementary Multiperspective Material Ontology (EMMO)

EU – European Union

FLASK PYTHON - is a web framework and a Python module that lets one develop web Applications easily. It was developed by Armin Ronacher.

FOSS – Free and Open-Source Software

FSP - Flame Spray Pyrolysis

H2020 – Horizon 2020 is the financial instrument implementing the Innovation Union, a Europe 2020 flagship initiative aimed at securing Europe's global competitiveness. (2014-2020)

HPC – high performance computing

IRI - Internationalized Resource Identifiers

JSON - JavaScript Object Notation

L-PBF - laser powder bed fusion

NMBP - Nanotechnologies, Advanced Materials, Biotechnology, and Advanced Manufacturing and Processing

PF - Phase Field

OSP – Open Simulation Platform

REST API - RESTful API, *“...is an architectural style for an Application program interface (API) that uses HTTP requests to access and use data. That data can be used to GET, PUT, POST and DELETE data types, which refers to the reading, updating, creating and deleting of operations concerning resources.”* Quote from (Gillis, 2020)

SaaS – Simulation as a Service

SDK – Software Development Kit

SME – Small and Medium Enterprises

SPH - Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics

SWO – Software Owners

Tcl - Tool Command Language

UC1 – Use-case 1

UC2 – Use-case 2

UC3 – Use-case 3

UC4 – Use-case 4

UC5 – Use-case 5

UC6 – Use-case 6

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Figure 3. Strawberry Fruit on Brown Wooden Surface, by Ylanite Koppens; Green Mint Photo, by icon0.com; Flowers on a Cocktail Glass by RODNAE Productions; Orange and Yellow Straw, by Christopher; Purple Flowers with Green Leaves, by Ellie Burgin; Person Holding Straw on a Cocktail, by cottonbro.; modified by Alexandra Simperler.

Figure 4. Person Sitting on Gray Sofa While Using Macbook, by Pixabay; Person Holding Laboratory Flask, by Chokniti Khongchum; Group of People Having a Meeting, by Mikael Blomkvist; Two Men Holding Two Gray Metal Tools, by Kateryna Babaieva, modified by Alexandra Simperler.

Figures 5-9 are screenshots from the actual MarketPlace Platform, <https://www.materials-marketplace.eu/>.

Figure 11, with kind permission of ©C. Bierwisch, Fraunhofer IWM.

Figure 21 was created by HES.

Figure 27. Mountain Under Cloudy Sky, by Philip Ackermann; Grayscale Photography of Building, by Huie Dinwiddie; adapted by Alexandra Simperler

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